

Sports and Leadership Among Higher Education Students: A Bibliographic Analysis Based on The Web of Science Database

Yükseköğretim Öğrencilerinde Spor ve Liderlik: Web of Science Veritabanına Dayalı Bibliyometrik Bir Analiz

Mücahit DURSUN¹, Ceren ŞENGÜL²

*Correspondence:

Mücahit Dursun

E-mail:

mucahit.dursun@selcuk.edu.tr

¹Selcuk University, Faculty of Sports Sciences, Konya, Türkiye
mucahit.dursun@selcuk.edu.tr,
0000-0002-7786-0741

²Atatürk University, Faculty of Sports Sciences, Erzurum, Türkiye
ceren.sengul22@ogr.atauni.edu.tr,
0009-0006-7843-7298

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18937082>

Received / Gönderim: 12.11.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 12.02.2026

Published / Yayın: 28.02.2026

Volume 3, Issue 1, February, 2026

Cilt 3, Sayı 1, Şubat, 2025

Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the interdisciplinary relationship between sport and leadership through a comprehensive bibliometric analysis. A total of 886 publications indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) database were identified using an advanced search in the abstract field in the first quarter of 2026. The data were analysed using Bibliometrix R and VOSviewer software. The analysis includes annual publication trends, journal productivity, citation averages, international author collaborations, keyword co-occurrences, and conceptual network structures. Furthermore, the thematic evolution and temporal development of research topics were visualised through trend topic maps and co-occurrence networks. The results show that when examining the scientific production trend, a gradual increase in production began in 2005, reaching its first significant peak in 2012. From 2015 onwards, the literature gained its main momentum, and conceptual integration also increased. The findings show that sport in a university context has evolved from being solely a physical performance-oriented activity to a multidimensional field associated with leadership, identity development, life skills, and psychosocial gains. Overall, this study maps the current literature landscape and provides a comprehensive summary of the field's current state, offering a guiding framework for future theoretical and empirical research.

Keywords Bibliometric analysis, sport, leadership, students.

ÖZ

Bu çalışma, spor ve liderlik arasındaki disiplinlerarası ilişkiyi kapsamlı bir bibliyometrik analiz yoluyla incelemek amacıyla gerçekleştirilmiştir. 2026 yılının ilk çeyreğinde, Web of Science (WoS) veri tabanında özet alanında yapılan gelişmiş bir tarama sonucunda toplam 886 yayın belirlenmiştir. Elde edilen veriler Bibliometrix R ve VOSviewer yazılımları kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Analiz kapsamında yıllara göre yayın eğilimleri, dergi üretkenliği, atıf ortalamaları, uluslararası yazar iş birlikleri, anahtar kelime eş-oluşumları ve kavramsal ağ yapıları incelenmiştir. Ayrıca araştırma konularının tematik evrimi ve zamansal gelişimi, trend konu haritaları ve eş-oluşum ağları aracılığıyla görselleştirilmiştir. Elde edilen sonuçlar, bilimsel üretim eğilimi incelendiğinde 2005 yılında kademeli bir artışın başladığını ve 2012 yılında ilk önemli zirveye ulaştığını göstermektedir. 2015 yılından itibaren ise literatürün asıl ivmesini kazandığı ve kavramsal bütünleşmenin de arttığı görülmektedir. Bulgular, üniversite bağlamında sporun yalnızca fiziksel performansa dayalı bir etkinlik olmaktan çıkarak liderlik, kimlik gelişimi, yaşam becerileri ve psikososyal kazanımlar ile ilişkilendirilen çok boyutlu bir alan hâline geldiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Genel olarak bu çalışma, mevcut literatürün genel görünümünü haritalandırmakta ve alanın güncel durumuna ilişkin kapsamlı bir özet sunarak gelecekte yapılacak kuramsal ve ampirik araştırmalar için yol gösterici bir çerçeve ortaya koymaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler Bibliyometrik analiz, spor, liderlik, öğrenciler.

<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/v3-11/ijoss-Volume3-issue1-29.pdf>

Introduction

Although the term “sport” has become widespread globally due to the influence of English, it is not originally an English word. It is derived from the Latin roots “Disportere” or “Deportere” meaning “to scatter” or “to separate.” This word underwent changes during its usage, first evolving into ‘Disport’ and then, starting in the 17th century, into ‘Sport’. In Turkish, thanks to interactions between world languages, the word “Sport” was adopted and integrated into our language as “spor”, in accordance with its pronunciation (Çankaya, 2001).

The concept of sport has been addressed in different contexts and expressed with various definitions by many people who have a greater or lesser interest in this field. Some of these are as follows: Sport is an activity that strengthens the skills acquired by an individual in the process of transforming their natural environment into a human structure, performed with or without equipment, either individually or collectively, as a leisure activity or as a full-time profession, which strengthens social bonds, unites communities, matures the body and spirit, and is a competitive, collaborative and cultural phenomenon (Kılıçgil, 1998).

Sport is an activity that offers individuals a peaceful outlet for their innate aggressive tendencies, creating an ideal competitive arena for managing these feelings. It also arises from the skilful combination of physical activities and games, gifting us with the purest of emotions. Sport is one of the most common structures within society. Undoubtedly, sport consists of a series of events that play a critical role in human life and social welfare in its most limited and comprehensive dimensions (Özbaydar, 1983; Fişek, 1985).

Yetim (1996) described leadership as the capacity to persuade others in order to realise certain goals with enthusiasm and motivation, noting that this concept involves interaction between managers and those being managed. He also considered it an indispensable function for an effective manager. Koçel (2005), preferring the term “leadership” instead, defined it as the process of directing and influencing the actions of others to achieve individual or organisational goals under certain conditions. In this process, he drew attention to the role of interpersonal relationships. Bass (1990), who has made significant contributions to leadership literature, interprets leadership in various ways, such as a group-focused approach, an individual quality, a persuasion method that creates harmony between people, an attempt to guide others, a power dynamic, a means of achieving goals, or the foundation of a formation. The term leader is defined as a pioneering, guiding individual who anticipates the expectations and needs of followers and is innovative, while leadership is described as the ability to motivate and maintain harmony among staff in order to achieve the goals of the relevant organisation (Tunçer, 2012). Kılınç (2019) expresses leadership as directing the organisation according to its current and future needs, creating a harmonious and effective working environment by increasing employee motivation, permanently solving organisational problems, and simplifying the achievement of goals. Based on these definitions in the literature, a unifying definition can be summarised as the knowledge, ability, and skill to unite individuals within a specific community around common goals and motivate them to take action (Eren, 2014). The most critical element in this motivation phase is the

power of a person with leadership qualities to influence others. Leadership is also the act of initiating a call for transformation (Karakaplan Özer, 2019). Global changes are transforming companies into more innovative and adaptable structures, and success in this process depends on the effectiveness of organisational leaders and their power to motivate their organisations towards change (Yeşil, 2013). Leader figures have been seen throughout all periods of history, and it is clear that they will remain an indispensable element in management paradigms in the future (Tunçer, 2012; Eren, 2014). In contemporary societies, individuals participate in organisations, play sports, or engage in leisure activities in many areas, from education to work, health services to leisure activities (Yetim, 1996; Güzel vd., 2025). From this perspective, leadership manifests itself in every corner of life, from children's games to classroom environments, from the political arena to civil society or commercial organisations.

Leadership, as in general management disciplines, stands out as a fundamental element and one of the defining characteristics in the sports industry, both in on-field applications and in other sports-related activities (Gündoğdu, 2014). Sports management is of critical value in terms of leadership for the establishment of sports organisations and the optimal management of operational processes and activities. Sports administrators play a vital role in the implementation and effective maintenance of sports strategies at local and global levels. Sports administration is a profession that requires both sector-specific and administrative knowledge, along with qualities consistent with the fundamental goals and principles of sport (Yetim, 1996). Among these qualities, the most prominent and prioritised is providing exemplary leadership to subordinates, athletes, and their immediate environment (Kılınç, 2013). Due to sport being a social structure and its focus being on people, the need for individuals in sports administration to possess leadership qualities becomes even more pronounced (Yetim, 1996). Particularly in the field of sport, which is focused on winning and superiority, a sports administrator who possesses leadership qualities beyond being a qualified administrator increases their competitive advantage in both local and international arenas and accelerates their achievement of victory. It is essential for sports administrators to know which leadership approaches to choose under which conditions or to recognise their own dominant leadership characteristics in order to guide their audience and achieve goals (Gündoğdu, 2014). The fundamental qualities that a leader operating in the sports sector must acquire can be listed as the ability to delegate responsibility, the capacity to broaden the horizons of their audience, dedication to the common goals of the organisation and team, sensitivity to social, organisational and cultural norms, and predictive and intuitive awareness of potential threats (Gökçe, 2005). Under the powerful effects of globalisation today, it is imperative for an effective sports administrator to adopt a leadership model that is sensitive and credible towards their staff and can be a source of motivation and inspiration for their audience and athletes (Gündoğdu, 2014). Leaders should reinforce the sense of loyalty by emphasising the concepts of friendship and camaraderie within the team or organisation (Terlemez, 2019). Furthermore, in the sports world, where the pursuit of success is intense, it is essential for leaders to be passionate and determined, as well as tolerant and inclined to learn and progress. When reviewing leadership definitions in the sports sector, it is

described as “a mechanism that channels individuals and communities in the field of sports towards goals and shapes their attitudes” (Çelik, 2016). Donuk (2006) describes a leader as an individual who maximises the potential of the members of an organisation, creates the groundwork for this purpose, and encourages them. Although coaches are a dominant figure in the literature on sports leadership, the sports industry has a complex structure encompassing various dimensions. Within the scope of sports leadership, in addition to coaches, numerous examples can be listed, such as administrators in sports clubs, presidents and sub-unit managers in federations, the president and members of the Turkish Olympic Committee, managers of sports broadcasts in the media sector, or youth and sports provincial directors in local organisations, provincial delegates of federations and provincial referees committee presidents, or administrators of sports facilities and events.

Although studies in the fields of sport and leadership are increasing, research that evaluates sources bibliometrically using a holistic approach is limited (Arthur et al. 2017). Bibliometric studies shed light on the dynamics of scientific progress in the field by identifying publication trends, reference networks, subject clusters, and intellectual structures (Donthu et al. 2021, Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). It is observed that bibliometric studies focused on sports sciences are beginning to increase in our country, but there are still few studies that comprehensively address the connection between sports and leadership (Yüzer & Uğurlu 2025, Akpınar, 2023).

These data emphasise that, although publications on sport and leadership are growing in our country, there is a need for bibliometric tools to regularly interpret scientific output orientations, partnership links, and subject groups. In line with this need, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What is the general bibliometric picture of studies on leadership and sport among university students between 1987 and 2026?
- Which core journals have the highest publication productivity and academic impact in this literature?
- What is the global distribution of scientific production, and how is the intellectual flow between countries, authors, and key concepts shaped?
- Which sub-disciplines of the field are reflected by the most frequently used keywords in the literature and the thematic clusters formed by these keywords?
- What are the maturity and importance levels of existing themes in the field (motor themes, niche themes, fundamental themes), and what strategic gaps do they point to for future research?

The main objective of this study, shaped around these questions, is to assess the link between sport and leadership using bibliometric tools and to fill the knowledge gaps in the relevant discipline. The review aims to provide both theoretical and application-oriented advances in the field of sports science by interpreting the relationship between sport and leadership using a bibliometric evaluation model.

Material and Methods

Research Model

This study employed a bibliometric analysis method. The research has a descriptive bibliometric design that incorporates both performance analysis and scientific mapping approaches. Within this scope, the relationships between publication productivity, citation structures, sources, countries, authors, and keywords were analysed quantitatively. Bibliometric analysis is recognised as an effective method for revealing the structural characteristics, development trends, and intellectual networks of scientific production in a specific field (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017; Samiee & Chabowski, 2012).

Scope of the Research and Data Collection

The data used in the research were obtained from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database on 7 January 2026. The literature search was conducted using the keywords “Leadership”, “University Students” and “Sport” in all fields. During the search process, the keywords were combined using the Boolean operator as “Leadership AND University Students AND Sport”. This search yielded a total of 977 publications. The quantitative distribution of publication indexes was SSCI: 470, SCI-E: 239, A&HCI: 6, ESCI: 360 (includes common indexes), and 886 data were included in the analysis according to the specified indexes. The quantitative data obtained were analysed using the Bibliometrix R package biblioshiny interface. Screenshots of the data are provided as figures in the findings section. The analysis process was structured to enable a multidimensional examination of trends in the literature.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the scan

Figure 2. Creating a research design using the PRISMA method

The research design presented in Figure 2 utilises the PRISMA flow diagram to enhance the transparency of the data collection and screening process in the study. The PRISMA method has been used as a visual guide to clearly present the process of creating the dataset in bibliometric studies.

Ethical Statement: This study has been evaluated in accordance with the 2020 ULAKBİM TR Index Ethics Committee Principles. There were no experimental applications, surveys, interviews, observations, or interventions conducted on human or animal participants during the research process. The study was conducted entirely using secondary data (bibliometric data) and does not fall within the scope of research requiring ethical committee approval. Throughout all stages of the research, the principles of scientific research and publication ethics, academic integrity rules, and ethical responsibilities regarding data use were strictly adhered to.

Findings

This section of the study presents quantitative findings regarding the analysis results of the data.

Figure 3. General Information

As shown in Figure 3, the general information provided covers a period from 1987 to 2026, with a total of 886 documents published in 403 different sources analysed. This literature, which has an annual growth rate of 2.86%, has an average document age of 7.36; it was determined that the studies received an average of 18.98 citations per document and contained a total of 35,891 references. An examination of the author structure in the field revealed that 7,372 authors contributed to the process, with a high average of 11.3 authors per document and an international collaboration rate of 22.12%. This dataset, which utilised a total of 2,442 different author keywords, indicates that the field possesses a multidisciplinary and robust academic interaction network.

Figure 4. Annual Scientific Output

When examining Figure 4, which shows the annual scientific production trend for the period 1987-2026, the development process of the literature can be divided into three main phases. In the first phase, from 1987 to the early 2000s, the number of publications was quite low and remained stable. A gradual increase in production began in 2005, reaching its first significant peak in 2012. From 2015 onwards, the literature gained significant momentum, with the annual number of publications rising rapidly, exceeding the 100-article threshold in 2025 to reach its highest level.

Figure 5. Most Relevant Sources

Based on Figure 5, the Sport Management Education Journal stands out as the most prolific publication in the field with 36 documents. It is followed by the Journal for the Study of Sports and Athletes in Education (25 documents) and the Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education (24 documents). Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy and Recreational Sports Journal are other key outlets contributing significantly to the literature with 22 publications each. This distribution indicates that academic discussions are predominantly centred on sport pedagogy, management, and

educational outcomes; it also shows that interdisciplinary sources such as *Frontiers in Psychology* (19 documents) have considerable visibility in the field.

Country Scientific Production

Figure 6. Geographical Distribution of Scientific Output

When interpreting Figure 6, the United States stands out as the leading country with the highest publication volume in the field, represented by the darkest colour. Following North America, European countries, Australia and China also make significant contributions to the field, while production remains more limited in certain regions of South America and Africa. This distribution confirms that academic interest is concentrated in developed economies, but that the subject is a globally recognised area of research at an international level.

Figure 7. Three-Field Graph

As shown in Figure 7, the diagram illustrating the relationship between references, authors, and keywords demonstrates that the literature is built upon the themes of ‘health,’ ‘physical activity,’ and ‘education.’ It is evident that fundamental methodological sources such as Creswell (2006) and Hair (1998) define the academic framework in this field. Leading authors such as Smith Lee and Vancampfort Davy have been found to dominate health and motivation-focused concepts, placing them at the centre of this interdisciplinary interaction.

quadrant's topics such as 'life skills,' 'physical activity,' and 'motivation' form the fundamental building blocks upon which the literature is constructed but which remain open to theoretical development.

Discussion

The bibliometric findings of this study reveal that academic output in the fields of leadership and sport among university students has increased significantly over the past forty years, gaining particular momentum since 2010. This increase in annual scientific output indicates that sport is no longer viewed solely as a physical performance and competition-focused activity within the university context; rather, it is increasingly being recognised as a multidimensional development area linked to leadership development, identity formation, life skills, and psychosocial gains. The establishment of the concepts of "leadership", "sport", and "education" at the intellectual centre in keyword and network analyses is also an important indicator supporting this transformation.

These findings largely coincide with the current literature examining the role of sport in leadership development. Studies conducted in a university context reveal that participation in sport makes a meaningful contribution to the development of skills such as leadership capacity, leadership self-efficacy, responsibility-taking and teamwork; this process also supports students' academic and social adjustment (Correia-Harker et al., 2025; Gould & Voelker, 2012). In light of this information, the increase in production identified bibliometrically reflects the growing interest in the literature in repositioning sport as an educational and personal development tool.

On the other hand, it is observed that leadership in sports environments is not solely a role reserved for coaches; the concept of athlete leadership is increasingly being addressed at both theoretical and practical levels. Studies examining approaches to developing athlete leadership show that leadership has acquired a multi-actor structure related to team interactions, motivational climate, and psychosocial adjustment (Cotterill & Loughhead, 2022; Turnnidge & Côté, 2017). This situation is consistent with the identification of leadership and sports management themes as 'niche themes' in bibliometric analysis and suggests that the field has a structure that is specialised in certain sub-topics while also being open to deepening.

The identity development perspective constitutes another important conceptual framework explaining the effects of sport on leadership and personal development. Research adopting the 'identity work' approach reveals that athletic identity is dynamically renegotiated in line with academic expectations, life events, and social roles, and does not have a fixed structure (Chun et al., 2023). Similarly, studies examining academic and athletic identities together in student-athletes show that role conflicts and adaptation processes experienced in the dual career context are closely related to leadership development (Steele et al., 2020). These findings can be said to directly correspond to the inclusion of the concepts of 'student-athletes,' 'identity,' and 'higher education' among the motor themes in the thematic analysis.

The potential of sport to impart life skills also occupies a central position in both the empirical literature and bibliometric results. Experimental studies demonstrating the impact of sport-based interventions on life skills such as leadership, goal setting, and

problem solving show that gains acquired through sport can be transferred to other areas of life (Malete et al., 2022). Furthermore, meta-analytic studies synthesising the relationships between coaching leadership and athlete satisfaction, psychological adjustment, and group cohesion reveal that sports environments offer significant psychosocial gains (Zhu et al., 2024). Bibliometric findings indicate that the concepts of 'life skills,' 'motivation,' and 'physical activity' are fundamental but remain open to development, suggesting a need for more experimental and longitudinal research in these areas.

Finally, studies linking leadership in physical education and sport contexts to pedagogical outcomes address leadership as a holistic learning process encompassing cognitive, social, and emotional development beyond technical skills (Gould & Voelker, 2012). This approach is consistent with findings from bibliometric analysis showing that sport is structured as a multidisciplinary research field centred on education, health, and psychosocial development. It is considered that assessments suggesting the need to reposition sport as an educational and pedagogical tool in higher education should be strongly supported.

The findings obtained from the analyses reveal that the field of leadership and sport among university students is not merely a quantitatively growing literature; it has also acquired a distinct structure in conceptual, thematic, and methodological terms. However, to make the comprehensive picture presented by bibliometric analyses more meaningful, the fundamental dimensions of the field's development must be systematically addressed. Therefore, in the following section, based on the findings of the study, the general bibliometric overview of the literature, prominent journals, global production and intellectual flow patterns, thematic clusters, and the maturity and importance levels of themes are discussed in detail in line with the research questions.

General Bibliometric Overview for 1987–2026

The findings show that a total of 886 documents related to leadership and sports among university students were published in 403 different sources during the period 1987–2026, and that the annual growth rate of the literature was 2.86%. The average age of the documents is 7.36, and the average number of citations per document is 18.98. The production structure is highly collective in nature; 7,372 authors contributed, the number of authors per document reached a high value of 11.3, and the international collaboration rate was 22.12%. An examination of the annual production trend reveals a stagnant and low trajectory between 1987 and 2000, followed by a gradual increase after 2005 and a marked acceleration, particularly since the 2010s.

Gap/Recommendation: While this quantitative growth indicates that the field has entered a maturation phase, it can be argued that the increasing volume of publications needs to be supported by theoretical depth and causal evidence. Based on this information, it is recommended that longitudinal and intervention-based (programme evaluation) studies examining the variables that explain leadership development be increased.

Journals with the Highest Publication Productivity and Academic Impact

The analysis results show that the journals with the highest publication productivity in the literature are, respectively, the Sport Management Education Journal (36), the Journal for the Study of Sports and Athletes in Education (25), and the Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education (24). These are followed by Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy and the Recreational Sports Journal (22 publications each). Furthermore, the prominence of an interdisciplinary journal such as *Frontiers in Psychology* (19) indicates that leadership and sports studies are increasingly linked to psychology-based processes (such as motivation, well-being, and satisfaction).

Gap/Recommendation: The journal distribution shows that the field is distinctly divided along the axes of sports management–sports pedagogy–psychology. To reduce the theoretical disconnect between these axes in future research, it may be advisable to develop interdisciplinary publication strategies based on common theoretical frameworks such as the social identity approach, transformational leadership, and positive youth development/life skills.

Global Distribution of Scientific Output and Intellectual Flow

When examining the geographical distribution of scientific output, the United States stands out as the country with the highest output, while European countries, Australia and China also make significant contributions to the field. In contrast, it is noteworthy that production remains more limited in South America and Africa. The production dynamic exhibits a network-based structure, supported by an international collaboration rate of 22.12%. The three-field graph shows that intellectual flow is heavily concentrated on the themes of ‘health’, ‘physical activity’ and ‘education’; leadership and sports research form a strong reference-author-concept connection on the axis of health and pedagogy.

Gap/Recommendation: The concentration of scientific production in specific geographical centres may limit the generalisability of the findings. Therefore, it is recommended to increase comparative studies and international research collaborations addressing the leadership–sport relationship in different socio-cultural contexts (especially in developing countries) and to include cultural, gender and socio-economic variables more in analytical models.

Keywords and Sub-disciplines Reflected in Thematic Clusters

Network analysis and word cloud results reveal that the concepts of ‘leadership’, “sport” and ‘education’ are at the intellectual centre of the literature. The thematic clusters are divided into three main focuses:

- (i) leadership and motivational performance,
- (ii) physical activity and health,
- (iii) perception, gender and social dimensions in higher education.

This structure demonstrates that the field is not limited to sports management and pedagogy; it has a multidisciplinary character that integrates with public health and social sciences.

Gap/Recommendation: To strengthen the integration between thematic clusters, it is recommended that holistic models be developed within the same research design that simultaneously address leadership processes, health/well-being indicators, and social inequality variables.

Maturity and Importance Levels of Themes and Strategic Research Gaps

The thematic analysis results highlight the concepts of student-athletes, identity, and higher education as core themes. This indicates that student-athlete identity and the higher education context lie at the heart of the field, forming a mature orientation that drives the literature along this line. Niche themes (leadership, sport management) represent more specialised research areas, while fundamental but developing themes (life skills, physical activity, motivation) indicate areas upon which the literature is built but which require further theoretical and empirical reinforcement.

Gap/Recommendation: In this context, two key strategic research gaps emerge:

*Increasing intervention, experimental, and follow-up studies that test whether sport truly produces transferable gains along the life skills–motivation–physical activity continuum.

*Developing longitudinal research designs, as well as mediating and moderating models that explain how identity development relates to leadership outcomes along the student-athlete identity–higher education continuum.

Conclusion

This study presents the development of the literature on leadership and sport among university students between 1987 and 2026 from a bibliometric perspective. The findings show that academic production has increased significantly, particularly since 2010, and that sport in a university context has evolved from being solely a physical performance-oriented activity to a multidimensional field associated with leadership, identity development, life skills, and psychosocial gains.

The thematic structure of the literature reveals that the student-athlete identity and the higher education context are central to the field; conversely, it highlights that life skills, motivation, and physical activity themes are important research areas that need to be developed. In this respect, the study provides a comprehensive summary of the current state of the field and offers a guiding framework for future theoretical and empirical research.

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde “Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi” kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir.

citation rules were followed in accordance with the ‘Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Guidelines’; no alterations were made to the collected data, and this study has not been submitted for

evaluation to any other academic publication medium. The author is solely responsible for any violations that may arise in connection with this article. All participants voluntarily participated in this study.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Yazar Katkıları / Authors' Contribution Statement

M.D. ve C.Ş., çalışmanın kavramsallaştırılması, tasarımı, veri toplama, analiz, yorumlama ve makalenin hazırlanması süreçlerinin tamamına katkı sağlamıştır.

M.D. and C.Ş. contributed to the conception, design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and manuscript preparation.

Fon Desteği / Funding

This Bu çalışma, kamu, özel veya kar amacı gütmeyen sektörlerdeki fon sağlayıcı kurumlardan herhangi bir özel destek almamıştır.

This research received no external funding.

Teşekkür / Acknowledgements

None.

References / Kaynaklar

- Akpınar, Ö. (2023). Sporda Liderlik Alanında Yapılan Çalışmaların Bibliyometrik Analizi. *Eurasian Journal of Sport Sciences and Education*, 5(2), 116-132. <https://doi.org/10.47778/ejsse.1325523>
- Aria, M., & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). Bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959-975. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>
- Arthur, C. A., Bastardo, N., & Eklund, R. (2017). Transformational leadership in sport: Current status and future directions. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 16, 78-83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2017.04.001>
- Atasoy, B., & Kuter, F. Ö. (2005). Küreselleşme ve spor. *Uludağ Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 18(1), 11-22.
- Bass, B. (1990). *Bass & Stogdill's Handbook of Leadership: Theory, Research and Managerial Applications*. New York: The Free Press.
- Chun, Y., Wendling, E., & Sagas, M. (2023). Identity work in athletes: A systematic review of the literature. *Sports*, 11(10), 203. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports11100203>.
- Correia-Harker, B. P., Clark, L. M., & Capin, J. J. (2025). Do sports develop leadership? The impact of college varsity sports on leadership capacity and self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 7, Article 1691139. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2025.1691139>.
- Cotterill, S. T., Loughhead, T. M., & Fransen, K. (2022). Athlete leadership development within teams: Current understanding and future directions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 820745. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.820745>.
- Çankaya, C., (2001). Spor tesisleri işletmeciliği ve planlama ders notları. *Physical education of students*, 1(1), 1-92.
- Çelik, V. O. (2016). *Sporda Yönetim Uygulamaları ve Liderlik*. R. Ekmekçi içinde, *Sporda Yönetim ve Organizasyon*. İstanbul: Ergün Yayınevi.
- Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., & Lim, W. M. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of business research*, 133, 285-296.
- Donuk, B. (2006). Türkiye profesyonel futbol ligleri antrenörlerinin liderlik tarzlarının incelenmesi ve bir model yaklaşım. Marmara Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü (Doktora tezi), İstanbul
- Eren, E. (2014). *Örgütsel Davranış ve Yönetim Psikolojisi*. İstanbul: Beta Yayıncılık.

- Esin Yüzer, İ., & Uğurlu, A. (2025). Son 10 Yılda Spor Yönetimi Alanında Yapılmış Olan Çalışmaların Bibliyometrik Analizi. *ADÜ-Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(2), 115-136.
- Fişek, K. (1985). 100 soruda Türkiye spor tarihi. İstanbul: Gerçek Yayınevi.
- Gould, D., & Voelker, D. K. (2012). Enhancing youth leadership through sport and physical education. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 83(8), 38-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2012.10598828>.
- Gökçe, Z. (2005). Spor yönetiminin farklı boyutlarında yer alan spor yöneticilerinin liderlik tiplerinin araştırılması (Ege bölgesi örneği). Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Celal Bayar Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Manisa.
- Gündoğdu, F. (2014). Spor yöneticilerinin liderlik stilleri ile sporun yaygınlaştırılması arasındaki ilişki. Ankara Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Anabilim Dalı,(Basılmamış Doktora Tezi). Ankara.
- Güzel, S., Yaman, M. S., Yel, K., Çakır, Z., Gönen, M., Ceyhan, M. A., & Aydemir, B. (2025). Farklı Branşlardaki Spor Etkinliklerine Katılan Bireylerin Gönüllü Motivasyon Durumlarının İncelenmesi. *Dede Korkut Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 3(2), 241-265. <https://doi.org/10.71243/dksbd.1824551>
- İnan, Ö. İ., & Serinkan, C. (2020). Liderlik yaklaşımları ve spor yönetiminde liderlik. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(2), 308-332. <https://doi.org/10.47097/piar.824025>
- Karakaplan Özer, E. (2019). Etkili Liderlik ile Duygusal Bağlılık İlişkisinde İşveren Markası Algısının Aracılık Etkisi ve Araştırma. İnönü Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, (Basılmamış Doktora Tezi). Malatya.
- Kılıçgil, E. (1998). Sosyal çevre-spor ilişkileri:(Teori ve elit sporculara ilişkin bir uygulama). Ankara: Bağırçan Yayınevi.
- Kılınç, E. (2019). Stratejik ve dönüşümcü liderlik ile işgören performansı ilişkisi: Sağlık sektöründe bir araştırma. İnönü Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi, Malatya.
- Kılınç, Z. (2013). Kadın spor yöneticilerinin labirentteki yolculuğu: liderlik becerileri, algılanan engeller ve toplumsal cinsiyet rolleri. Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Spor Yöneticiliği Ana Bilim Dalı,(Basılmamış Doktora tezi).
- Koçel, T. (2005). İşletme Yöneticiliği. İstanbul: Arıkan Basım Yayım Dağıtım.
- Malete, L., McCole, D., Tshube, T., Mphela, T., Maro, C., Adamba, C., ... & Ocansey, R. (2022). Effects of a sport-based positive youth development program on youth life skills and entrepreneurial mindsets. *Plos one*, 17(2), e0261809. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261809>.
- Özbaydar, S. (1983). İnsan davranışının sınırları ve spor psikolojisi. Altın Kitaplar.
- Samiee, S., & Chabowski, B. R. (2012). Knowledge structure in international marketing: A multi-method bibliometric analysis. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing science*, 40(2), 364-386.
- Steele, A. R., van Rens, F. E. C. A., & Ashley, R. (2020). A systematic literature review on the academic and athletic identities of student-athletes. *Journal of Intercollegiate Sport*, 13(1), 69-92. <https://doi.org/10.17161/jis.v13i1.13502>.
- Terlemez, M. (2019). Sporda Liderlik Tipleri, Yaklaşımları ve Fonksiyonları. *Oğuzhan Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 138-151.
- Tunçer, P. (2012). Yönetim ve Organizasyon. İstanbul: Beta Yayıncılık.
- Turnidge, J. & Côté, J. (2017) Transformational coaching workshop: applying a person-centred approach to coach development programs. *International Sport Coaching Journal* 4(3), 314-325. <https://doi.org/10.1123/iscj.20170046>
- Yeşil, S. (2013). Küresel ve Değişen Çevre Dinamikleri Işığında Yeni Yönetim Yaklaşımlarından Seçme Konular. Ankara: Şeçkin Yayıncılık.
- Yetim, A. A. (1996). Spor Yönetiminde Liderlik. *Beden Eğitimi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1 (3), 85- 94.
- Zhu, J., Wang, M., Cruz, A. B., & Kim, H.-D. (2024). Systematic review and meta-analysis of Chinese coach leadership and athlete satisfaction and cohesion. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1385178. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1385178>.

Publishers' Note

IJOSS remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.